

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

ALGORITHM FOR SELECTING A FLOW METER WITH OPTIMAL PARAMETERS

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Abstract

The paper deals with the selection process of the optimal gas flow meter for information-measuring system. Criteria for selection of the flow meters are studied. The algorithm based on Analytical Hierarchy Process method and Technique for Order Preference by Similar to the Ideal Solution for selection of the gas flow meter is proposed. The application of the proposed algorithm increases reliability of the final decision. and enables automation of the selection process by using software.

Keywords: Gas Flow Meter, Selecting Algorithm, Multi-Criteria, Decision Making

1. Introduction

In many cases, the problem arises of choosing from a variety of alternatives to measuring instruments necessary for measuring the parameters of a technological process. This is due to the fact that measuring instruments with different designs, operating principles and different technical and technological parameters are produced by different manufacturers. One of these measuring instruments is a gas flow meter. At present, flow meters of various designs with a simple operating principle are used to measure and account for the flow (amount) of gas. The information and measurement systems to which these devices and devices are connected can also be built on the basis of various concepts. Accurate measurements and metering of natural gas during production, transportation and distribution is very important in terms of optimizing these processes. One of the most important problems in the development of these systems is the selection of measuring instruments with optimal operational and metrological characteristics in accordance with the manufacturer's specifications and the terms of reference for the system design. Naturally, such a choice is made using existing

criteria and methods, based on information about the principle of operation of these devices, about the parameters that determine their design, about metrological indicators (accuracy and error, etc.), methods of receiving and transmitting information, about operating temperature and pressure, about the type of output signal and the functionality of measuring instruments [1].

2. Assigning the Problem

This multi-criteria decision-making problem contains different and conflicting criteria. Therefore, after analyzing the necessary parameters of the flow meters included in the set for selection, these flow meters were selected finally by experts according to four main criteria: C1-accuracy, C2-reliability, C3-survivability, C4-price and cost of maintenance. Finally, we will solve the problem of selecting a flow meter from the resulting series with alternatives A, B, C, D (see Section 3).

The relative importance between the two criteria for selecting of the gas flow meter is measured on a numerical scale from 1 to 9, as represented in Table 1.

Table 1. Relative importance.

Value	Interpretation
1	j and k equally important
3	j is slightly more important than k
5	j is strongly more important than k
7	j is very strongly more important than k
9	j is absolutely strongly more important than k

Table 2 shows the ratings of linguistic performances according to various criteria.

Table 2. Linguistic performance rating

Criteria	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4
C_1	1	1/5	1/3	5
C_2	5	1	5	1/7
C_3	3	1/5	1	3
C_4	1/5	7	1/3	1

Pairwise comparisons are not required if the items being compared are expressed in the same units and using an appropriate precision meter. The answer to the question of how important one item is over another is presented as a simple combination of the dimensions of all items.

So, let's solve the problem of choosing a gas flow meter for an information-measuring system according to many criteria using an algorithm proposed below.

3. Solution to the Problem

This algorithm is a combination of the AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) and TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similar to the Ideal Solution - TOPSIS) methods. AHP, proposed by Saaty, is a multi-criterial decision-making method used to assess and determine the importance of relative weights for decision criteria [2].

The algorithm is widely used to analyze and structure complex decision-making problems. The decision-making process is initially divided into various criteria. The AHP method can be used to assist decision-makers in calculating weights for each criterion and evaluating them by pairwise comparison. AHP has attracted the interest of many researchers, mainly because of the excellent mathematical properties of the method and the ease of obtaining the required input data. The AHP method is a stable and flexible decision-making tool in a multi-criteria environment for solving complex decision-making problems. This method separates a complex system into a system of hierarchical elements, usually consisting of goals, evaluation criteria and alternatives. The assessment criteria level can be composed of various assessment criteria, which can be extended to a multi-level structure. There are the following main steps of the AHP methodology:

Step 1: Setting up the decision matrix. The rows of the decision matrix contain the alternatives that are given priority, and the columns contain the criteria used in making decisions. This matrix is the original matrix created by the decision maker. The decision matrix is displayed as follows:

$$A_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where m-is the number of alternatives, n-is the number of evaluation factors - criteria.

$$A^* = \left\{ \left(\max_i v_{ij} \mid j \in J \right), \left(\min_i v_{ij} \mid j \in J \right) \right\}; A^* = \{v_1^*, v_2^*, \dots, v_n^*\} \quad (5)$$

Step 4: The set of negative ideal solutions chooses the largest of the values in the columns of the matrix Vij (the largest when the corresponding criterion is

$$A^- = \left\{ \left(\min_i v_{ij} \mid j \in J \right), \left(\max_i v_{ij} \mid j \in J \right) \right\}; A^- = \{v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_n^-\} \quad (6)$$

Step 5: Calculation of distance values. Distance from positive ideal solution

$$S_i^* = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^*)^2} \quad (7)$$

Distance from negative ideal solution

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2} \quad (8)$$

Step 2: Setting up the standard decision matrix Rij. The standard decision matrix is calculated using the elements of matrix A by the following formula:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^m a_{kj}^2}} \quad (2)$$

Matrix Rij matrix has the form:

$$R_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & \dots & r_{1n} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & \dots & r_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ r_{m1} & r_{m2} & \dots & r_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Step 3: Setting up the standard weighted decision matrix Vij.

$$V_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 r_{11} & w_2 r_{12} & \dots & w_n r_{1n} \\ w_1 r_{21} & w_2 r_{22} & \dots & w_n r_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ w_1 r_{m1} & w_2 r_{m2} & \dots & w_n r_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Step 4: Ranking the scenario, which is done by sorting the total points in descending order.

One of the multi-criteria decision-making models is the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution TOPSIS [2]. This method was developed to solve the problem of multi-criteria decision-making based on the concept that the chosen alternative is at the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution (A*) and the largest distance from the negative ideal solution (A-). The TOPSIS method is used to obtain the final rating. Some of the advantages of this method are simplicity, rationality, good understanding, good computational efficiency, and the ability to measure the relative capabilities of each alternative in a simple mathematical way. The chosen alternative should be located at the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution and at the greatest distance from the negative ideal solution.

The procedure of multi-criteria decision-making is given as follows [2]:

Step 1: Setting up the normalized decision matrix that transforms properties of different formula (2).

Step 2: Setting up the weighted normalized decision matrix using formula (4).

Step 3: Calculation of the positive ideal (A*) and negative ideal (A-) solutions. The TOPSIS method assumes that each factor - assessment criterion has a monotonically increasing or decreasing character. Calculation of the set of ideal solutions by the following formula:

maximized). The set of negative ideal solutions is calculated using the following formula:

Step 6. Calculation of the relative closeness to the ideal solution.

$$C_i^* = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^- + S_i^*} \quad (9)$$

Step 7. Priority row ranking: Alternatives C can be ranked in descending order.

Applying the steps described above we solve the problem of selection of the gas flow meter.

It is recommended to investigate the properties of the comparison matrix during accurate measurements. A pairwise comparison matrix is a consistent matrix for accurately comparing any number of items.

AHP is a powerful tool that can be used to make decisions when there are many conflicting criteria and both qualitative and quantitative aspects of the decision are taken into account. AHP allows to pairwise comparison of complex solutions.

First, using formula (2), we determine the preferences for the goals shown in Tables 1 and 2, and the weights calculated for these goals:

$$C_{11} = \frac{1}{\left(1 + 5 + 3 + \frac{1}{5}\right)} = 0,11$$

Average weight for

$$C_1 = \frac{(0,11 + 0,06 + 0,04 + 0,55)}{4} = 0,18$$

Other calculated weights (average)

$$C_2 = 0,36; C_3 = 0,21; C_4 = 0,25.$$

Table 4. Property and functionality values.

C_1	A	B	C	D	
A	1	1/3	5	1/3	
B	3	1	1/3	1/3	
C	1/5	3	1	5	
D	3	3	1/5	1	
C_1	A	B	C	D	Average
A	0.14	0.05	0.76	0.05	0.25
B	0.42	0.14	0.05	0.05	0.34
C	0.03	0.41	0.15	0.75	0.34
D	0.42	0.41	0.08	0.15	0.27

In the same way, we determine the relative values for other alternatives and results shown in table 4.

Table 5. Relative values for alternatives.

Criteria	A	B	C	D
C_1	0.25	0.34	0.34	0.27
C_2	0.05	0.44	0.31	0.25
C_3	0.21	0.38	0.36	0.40
C_4	0.51	0.01	0.29	0.19

Finally, we calculate the weights for the alternatives (Table 3) and rank them according to the relative values for every alternative (Table 4):

Table 3. Weights for criteria

Criteria	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	Average
C_1	0.11	0.06	0.04	0.55	0.18
C_2	0.54	0.12	0.75	0.015	0.36
C_3	0.33	0.02	0.15	0.33	0.21
C_4	0.02	0.83	0.05	0.11	0.25

At the next stage, we define for each alternative different relative criterion. The relative values of properties and functionality were calculated as examples and are shown in Table 4.

$$A = 0,25 \cdot 0,18 + 0,05 \cdot 0,36 + 0,21 \cdot 0,21 + 0,51 \cdot 0,25 = 0,045 + 0,018 + 0,044 + 0,127 = 0,23;$$

$$B = 0,34 \cdot 0,18 + 0,44 \cdot 0,36 + 0,38 \cdot 0,21 + 0,01 \cdot 0,25 = 0,061 + 0,0158 + 0,08 + 0,0025 = 0,25;$$

$$C = 0,34 \cdot 0,18 + 0,31 \cdot 0,36 + 0,36 \cdot 0,21 + 0,29 \cdot 0,25 = 0,061 + 0,011 + 0,075 + 0,11 = 0,25;$$

$$D = 0,27 \cdot 0,18 + 0,25 \cdot 0,36 + 0,40 \cdot 0,21 + 0,19 \cdot 0,25 = 0,049 + 0,09 + 0,084 + 0,047 = 0,27.$$

After ranking the alternatives, we determine that alternative D is better than the other alternatives.

The TOPSIS method is used to make a decision by computer, and the best alternative chosen would be the shortest distance from the ideal solution and the longest

distance from the negative ideal solution. After forming the normalized and weighted normalized matrix (table 6), we determine the ideal and negative ideal solutions by formulas (5) and (6):

Table 6. Weight Normalized Matrix.

	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4
A	0.25	0.05	0.21	0.51
B	0.34	0.44	0.38	0.01
C	0.34	0.31	0.36	0.29
D	0.27	0.25	0.40	0.19

At the next stage, the distance from the ideal solution and the distance from the negative ideal solution are calculated using formulas (7) and (8). Thus for alternative A we obtain:

$$S_A^* = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^4 (A_{ij} - A^*)^2} = (0,25 - 0,34) + (0,05 - 0,44) + (0,21 - 0,40) + (0,51 - 0,51) = 0,41$$

$$S_A^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^4 (A_{ij} - A^-)^2} = (0,25 - 0,25) + (0,05 - 0,05) + (0,21 - 0,21) + (0,51 - 0,01) = 0,5$$

Relative closeness to ideal solution is given by

$$C_A^* = \frac{S_A^-}{S_A^- + S_A^*} = \frac{0,5}{(0,41 + 0,5)} = 0,54$$

For the other alternatives we get

$$C_B^* = \frac{S_B^-}{S_B^- + S_B^*} = \frac{0,43}{(0,50 + 0,43)} = 0,46; C_C^* = \frac{S_C^-}{S_C^- + S_C^*} = \frac{0,42}{(0,29 + 0,42)} = 0,59; C_D^* = \frac{S_D^-}{S_D^- + S_D^*} = \frac{0,33}{(0,10 + 0,32)} = 0,78.$$

After ranking the alternatives, we find that alternative D is superior to the other alternatives.

Thus, taking into account the opinion of an expert or experts, using the AHP and TOPSIS methods, based on the selection criteria, we refine the decision on choosing a flow meter among alternatives, which is superior in parameters and indicators.

4. Conclusions

Proposed algorithm consisted of two methods uses initial information about selection of the required measurement device with optimal parameters.

Initial information prepared by experts, who study all technical and metrology parameters of the device and prepares information about alternative devices. This information is processed in the next stage to find

optimal device by the proposed algorithm, that allows to automate the decision making procedure.

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